

THE GIVING OF NATIONAL TRADITIONS IN STENDHAL'S RED AND BLACK AS WELL AS CHOLPON'S DAY AND NIGHT WORKS

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Abstract: In this article, the presentation of national customs in the red and black of the standal and the night and day works of the cholpon is highlighted.

Keywords: "collected, most garbage, from each craft" suggested, rule together, flavor of authenticity.

The novel "Red and black" grew on a creatively processed documentary basis: S. shocked by the fate of two young people sentenced to death: one of them, a young ambitious but extremely insignificant person, Berte shot at the mother. he is a girl who is the governor. The latter, the head of the Cabinet, Laffarg, who had a passion for philosophy and literature, was shy and proud. Falling in love with her, she refused, the girl accused her of trying to violence. In both cases S. saw the characteristic phenomenon of that time: society kills young people who left the third estate, striving if they do not obey the order. realization of their inner extraordinary potential. Prototypes had such characteristics, but we can say that S. we remember that he gave his hero "a little more intelligence."

In the novel, he created a typical image of the life of modern society. The author emphasizes in his appeal to the reader that the next pages were written in 1827. The authenticity of the date can be treated with caution, as in many signatures and epigraphs: the novel mentions the events that took place in France in 1829 and at its beginning. 30 years and many epigraphs were created by the author himself, although they belong to Gobbs, Machiavelli, Kant and others, in fact, only epigraphs of Shakespeare, Byron and antique authors are real. Why? As an artistic means of recreating the flavor of authenticity and expressed in images where the author's opinion is not always interpreted in a sense, for greater clarity. Sometimes the

signature had a secret, revolutionary direction: "true, bitter truth!"- the epigraph to the first part of the novel belongs to the head of the VFR, Danton. In the novel itself, the revolution is not mentioned, but the name Danton inevitably directs thought to 1789.

He repeatedly compares Julien Matilda with Danton, again connecting the characters with the revolutionary past and forcing us to think about a revolutionary future. The epigraph from Danton was replaced by the epigraph from Gobbes: "collect thousands of people - it does not look bad. But in a cage for them it will not be interesting. "The whole novel-research is directed against oppression, oppression of state power, religion, birth privileges. Creative tasks were also determined by the system of images: nobles - de Renali, bourgeoisie - Fuquet, Valno, priests - Abbot Shelan, Philistine - Soreli, regimental doctor of the Napoleonic army and Magistrate. The second group - Bezanson priests - seminarians, Abbot Pirard, Friler, Milon, Bishop. Outside Besanson is the bishop of Aghd. The highest aristocracy is De La Mol and visitors to his salon.

Modern S. The system of images, which allows extensive coverage of the life and conflicts of France, necessitated the construction of a novel divided into two parts, while events take place in 3 cities - Verrier (a fantastic provincial town), Bezanson. (seminary), Paris (high society, political life). The tension of the conflict increases with the approach of Paris, but personal interest and money reign everywhere. Married for Magic, The Aristocrat De Renal, in an attempt to withstand bourgeois competition, opened a factory, but at the end of the novel he still has to surrender - Valno becomes the mayor of the city. About Valno, the writer himself said at the beginning of the novel that he "collected the most garbage from each craft" and suggested to them: "let's rule together." S. He knows that in his time, such gentlemen as Valno became a socio-political force. Therefore, Valno dares to come to de La Mole, and the arrogant Marquis accepts the ignorant, hoping for his help during the election. "The Basic Law of everything that exists is to survive, to survive."

Political topics are organically included in the novel, combined with severe criticism of religion and scholars. Seminarian Julien thinks about the meaning of his clerical work: "Selling places in paradise to believers." S. calls the presence in the seminary, where future priests and teachers of the people are educated: "hypocrisy" reigns there, "thinking there is a crime", "healthy thinking is insulting". Abbot Pirard calls the priests "the poor who are necessary for the salvation of the soul." In the psychological novel of S., the priests take on the grotesque characteristics of the aristocracy and the bourgeoisie.

"Red and Black" is a socio-political novel, in which the features of an educational novel are clearly visible: in the first part, there is a young man who does not know life, who is amazed by everything he sees, and who is getting younger. begins to evaluate him, in the second part - a person who already has life experience, who decides to act independently, but in the end he comes to the conclusion that he is an "angry plebeian", he is still intelligent, active, honest. its core has no place in this world.

Striving to cover all areas of modern social life, S. Akin published his ml. Balzac's contemporary, but performs this task in a new way. The type of novel he created is distinguished by a chronicle-linear composition, which is unusual for Balzac, arranged by the biography of the hero. In this, S. aspires to the traditions of 18th century novelists, in particular Fielding, who is highly respected. However, unlike him, the author of "Red and Black" builds the plot not on the basis of adventure, but on the basis of the history of the spiritual formation of the hero, which is shown in a complex and dramatic effect with social services. wednesday The plot is based not on the plot, but on the action transferred to the soul and mind of Sorel, who rigorously analyzes the situation and himself in it each time before choosing an action that determines the further development of events. Hence the great importance of internal monologues, which involve the reader in the thoughts and feelings of the character. The work "An accurate and sincere image of the human heart" defines the

poetics of "Red and Black" as the most vivid example of the socio-psychological novel of the 19th century.

Chulpan, in the person of Enahan, expressed a sense of kindness along with the hospitality inherent in the Uzbek people. Enahan's call to the guests-the neighboring girls and brides-will show the kindness of people during that period, as well as beautiful manners.

In the work, as well as examples of manners, beautiful behavior characteristic of Uzbek girls, Khadichahan and his daughter acquire an interesting appearance in conversations between Virtue, Zebi and a stranger:

"As long as the table is a bit bad, you do not call, guests. We used to observe the earth as a resurrection...

- Say that! - said Pashshahan.

- I was not immersed in calling without asking you. The two of us consulted, and the day before the day the Sultan Khan called ayam."[2, 56 b.]

In a conversation between Virtue and her mother, the girl's beautiful behavior is manifested in decency. It's us.".. we can see clearly, clearly in the words □ I did not bother to call you without a request." The fact that she does not work beruxsat from her own mother, despite the fact that she is the only daughter of a wealthy household, indicates that the girl has a beautiful moral character.

In fact, for a person, manners, behavior and good upbringing outweigh any wealth. After all, things that cannot be found with wealth can be found with sympathy, beautiful treatment. Beautiful manners and behavior can close some of a person's faults and shortcomings. Beautiful behavior is a quality that not only beautifies the inner world of a person, but also manifests itself in his character. Zeby's beautiful demeanor and juicy voice make her respected among her friends. Many examples of Zeby's beautiful morals can be found in the work. In particular, even in his conversation with a stranger or in his position in the courtroom, such examples of decency can be seen: □- who are you? What do you say? - asked. From the side came a simple and slightly blurry, but cheerful male voice: - Yes, Are you the

weaklings of Razzak Sufi? Are you alive? - Thank God - put Zebi. - I would come to tell your father... - Must be asleep. Shall I wake up? Is it necessary? - My grandfather eshon destroyed. You can't wake up. "Fast, come forward!" they said.. - If there is no colt, let me wake up." [2, 113 b.] In this case, Zeby's headscarf can be panicked and come to the door, and his conversation with a stranger without opening the door, typical of Uzbek women, shows ibo-Haya and beautiful :his manners. His short interrogations in the series express the simplicity inherent in Uzbek girls: "The chairman of the court finally turned to tilmoch - Let your say open the guilty face. Tilmoch explained this command to Zeby.

- Wow, let's die! Will I open my face in front of so many nomahram? Is it better to die than him?" [2, 304 b.]

In this passage, Zeby's character and psyche are revealed extremely natural and lively. He is so simple and innocent that he does not even have an idea of the concept of a judicial prison. This naive Muslim woman, even when sitting in a black chair in court, thinks not about what the sentence will be, but about something completely different □ not to give a damn about the rules of Muslim, Sha'riat. The word □nomahram□, used in the passage, is a word that represents a religious meaning, meaning the opposite mahram of a man and a woman (in relation to each other) who are forbidden to see each other or appear to each other because of the lack of close kinship.

In conclusion, we can say that the language of the work is rich, attractive. Both the author's language and the language of the heroes are concise and figurative. The plot of the novel, combined with being beautiful and sergilo, is interesting and touching. Its coverage is much wider. Using only the image of the socio-personal relationship between the heroes of the novel □ Day and night", we tried to briefly interpret the Uzbek apartments of the beginning of the 20th century, the relations of spouses, virgins, neighbors and relatives in it, and some aspects characteristic of the Uzbek people and some traditions that are now disappearing.

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